

Supporting Information for 'Controlled Quantum-Dot Formation in Atomically-Engineered Graphene Nanoribbons Field-Effect Transistors'

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Characterisation of nanogaps before the transfer of the 5-AGNR film.

Figure 1: **Characterization of nanogaps before the transfer of the 5-AGNR film.** IV curves measured on device 1-4 shown in the main text before transfer of the 5-AGNR film. Each IV is the average of 5 back-and-forth voltage sweeps. For all devices, currents in the experimentally accessed range of $[-200 \text{ mV}, 200 \text{ mV}]$ do not exceed 5 pA, and remain below 25 pA for voltages up to 2 V.

Low temperature measurements

Figure 2: **Current Stability diagrams.** Current maps as a function of gate and bias voltage) of the devices presented in the main manuscript at 13 K.

Additional DFT calculations

Figure 3: Band structure of 5-AGNR

Figure 4: **Electronic properties of the 5-AGNR/graphene nanodevices** (a) Electrical conductance of the nanodevice consisting of a 5-AGNR bridging a graphene nanogap with ferromagnetic spin configuration. The insets give the results of a spin polarized wave function calculations. Spin density for b) ferromagnetic and c) antiferromagnetic spin configuration. The total energy of ribbons in (b,c) with antiferromagnetic (A) spin configuration is $E_A - E_F = -1.95meV$ lower than that of the ferromagnetic (F) one.

Figure 5: **Electrical conductance of the 5-AGNR/graphene nanodevices versus length** a) the nanodevice consisting of 5-AGNRs with various lengths bridging a graphene nanogap. In all junctions graphene/GNR overlap is fixed. b) Electrical conductance of the nanodevice with $N=10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ fused naphthalene units (N). c) Attenuation or conductance decay factor versus length¹ at $E_F = 0eV$ is $\beta = 0.6nm^{-1}$, d) the total energy differences between non-magnetic (non), ferromagnetic (F) and antiferromagnetic (A) GNRs with different lengths.

References

1. Sadeghi, Hatfeh; Theory of Electron, Phonon and Spin Transport in Nanoscale Quantum Devices, *Nanotechnology* **2018**, *29*, 373001.